

SIMPLIFICATION AS A TRANSLATION UNIVERSAL

1. Muydinov Jamshidbek Orifjon ugli

2. Khamidov Alisher Akhmatovich

1. 2nd year Graduate student of Faculty of Translation Theory and Practice
 Uzbekistan State World Languages University.

e-mail: jamshidbekmuydinov95@gmail.com

2. Senior Lecturer at Department of English language Translation Theory
 Uzbekistan State World Languages University.

e-mail: hamed88@bk.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7785309>

Annotation: This thesis aims to justify the fact that simplification is very essential one in interpreter education and synthesizing and presenting evidence from the current literature is focus of given thesis. It first defines the term „simplification” its theoretical concepts according to different literature.

Key words: simplification, theoretical concepts, simplification universal, translation.

Stylistic simplification involves breaking up longer sentences into shorter ones and constitutes one of the linguistic features assumed to typify translation, i.e. the purported translation universals. This set of features is believed to be characteristic of translated texts irrespective of the language pair in the translation process. The “universality” of universals is a debatable issue and there are also studies, in which not all hypothesized linguistic patterns are confirmed. Still, there is a range of features, which even if not universal per say, are more frequently found in translations than in non-translated texts. Over the years, translation scholars started to wonder whether the so-called universals are typical perhaps also of other forms of constrained communication, bilingual processing or mediated discourse . A recent strand of research investigates the existence of universals in the outcomes of other linguistic processes like editing . In short, it is possible that features long discussed mostly in the context of interlingua translation may be caused by a whole range of processes that are not unique to this one activity only. Although extensive, the literature on translation universals lacks publications reporting on comparative empirical studies of such features in inter- and intralingua translation. This is not surprising in the light of the fact that intralingua translation 1 The research presented in this article was funded by the Polish National Science Centre, grant no. Manuscript 2 as such generally has attracted scarce interest among translation scholars. Similarly, in the quest for translation universals researchers rarely step on board of translation process research. Investigations into universals started as case studies and with the advance of technology entered the area of corpus-based translation research, but they have not moved beyond this method for a very long time. Today, corpus based research on translation is slowly becoming complemented with other research methods but such studies are still few and far between. In the light of this rising trend and in order to provide greater insight into stylistic simplification, as well as to examine what process-related factors might be worth considering as related to mean sentence length, this paper combines corpus linguistics method with key logging and eye-tracking and focuses on a comparative analysis of the product and the process of inter- and intralingua translation carried out by professional translators and translation trainees. Simplification as a translation universal Next to explication, simplification is probably one of the most frequently discussed and

researched features belonging to the group of the hypothesized translation universals. Other features believed to distinguish translations from other texts include, among others, “growing grammatical conventionality and a tendency to over represent typical features of the target language as well as the feature of cleaning away repetitions from translations levelling out or underrepresentation of unique target language items. Chesterman distinguishes two types of translation universals: S-Universals, which “claim to capture universal differences between translations and their source texts, i.e. characteristics of the way in which translators process the source text” and T-Universals, which “make claims about universal differences between translations and comparable non-translated texts, i.e. characteristics of the way translators use the target language.” The set of S-Universals includes, e.g. lengthening, the tendency for translations to be longer than their source texts. Simplification is an example of a T-Universal and has most frequently, but not exclusively, been investigated with reference to non-translated texts. Simplification may be observed at three different levels: lexical, syntactic and stylistic. In this paper we focus on stylistic simplification, which may involve such linguistic operations as breaking up long sentences, using short collocations instead of elaborate ones, reducing repetitions and redundancies, shortening circumlocutions and leaving out modifiers. These operations have been observed already by Vanderauwera both in explicitly target accommodating translations and in those translations which could be “expected to adhere more closely to the source text.

The trajectory of this type is still very modest. They started by providing this service in conferences about subjects related to persons with cognitive disabilities in order to help them participate. In 2019, they received a request from the public Israeli television to do simultaneous simplification from English to Hebrew during the broadcast of Eurovision, a feat which placed the focus on this new linguistic service in Israel. Below, we would like to explain a few examples of the kind of simultaneous simplification that was carried out in Eurovision 2019 in order to better know what it is and be able to see it in context according to this article in pairs of original text (O) and the simplified version (S):

O: Welcome to the most fabulous room in the arena. This is the beating heart of the Eurovision contest – and I think I can hear ____ ‘s beating from here.

S: Welcome to this wonderful room. This room is called the green room. The green room is like the heart of the Eurovision contest. Can you feel your heart beating?

O: When this contest was launched sixty-four years ago, it was in the hope of bringing people together through the power of music.

S: The Eurovision contest was created many years ago. This contest hoped to make people feel together with the help of music.

With the goal of making this initiative more widely known, its promoters have started to work on training courses in which they explain what kind of audience would find simultaneous simplification useful, what their needs are, the basic principles of this discipline and practical sessions. There is no doubt that all the effort made to make understanding possible between different languages and different cognitive capacities are praiseworthy tasks.

As a concluding part we can surely say that Simplification in translation and interpretation is very initial one in order to comprehend in more easier language and it can be clear and obvious and without coloured words and long words.

References:

1. Bartłomiejczyk, Magdalena. 2006. "Strategies of Simultaneous Interpreting and Directionality." *Interpreting* 8(1): 149-174.
2. Bevilacqua, Lorenzo. 2009. "The Position of the Verb in Germanic Languages and Simultaneous Interpretation." *The Interpreters' Newsletter* 14: 1-31.
3. Calvo Encinas, Elisa. 2001. *La Evaluación Diagnóstica en la Didáctica de la Traducción Jurídica* [The Diagnostic Evaluation in the Teaching of Legal Translation]. Unpublished research paper, University of Granada, Spain.
4. Chang, Chia-Chien. 2005. *Directionality in Chinese/English Simultaneous Interpreting: Impact on Performance and Strategy Use*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Texas at Austin.
5. Chang, Chia-Chien, and Diane L. Schallert. 2007. "The Impact of Directionality on Chinese/English Simultaneous Interpreting." *Interpreting* 9(2): 137-176.
6. Chernov, Ghelly V. 2004. *Inference and Anticipation in Simultaneous Interpreting*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. 268 pp.
7. Chesterman, Andrew. 1993. "From 'is' to 'ought': Laws, Norms and Strategies in Translation Studies." *Target* 5(1): 1-20.